

Understanding and Managing Jungle Justice in Ibadan Metropolis

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Abstract

This study examines the management of the challenges of jungle justice in Ibadan Metropolis, Oyo State, Nigeria. Jungle justice, defined as the extrajudicial punishment of alleged offenders by mobs without recourse to due process, has persisted as a serious social and institutional concern. Anchored in the Self-Help Theory and Structural-Functionalist Theory, the study adopts a qualitative case study design to explore the drivers, management challenges, and mitigating strategies associated with this phenomenon. Data were obtained through nine in-depth and key informant interviews involving human rights advocates, community leaders, religious figures, legal practitioners, and scholars. Thematic analysis revealed that economic hardship, unemployment, political manipulation, institutional corruption, and loss of faith in the justice system are key drivers of mob violence. Management efforts such as public enlightenment, promotion of equity and fairness, improved education, and job creation were identified but found to be constrained by weak institutional capacity, poor funding, and limited grassroots engagement. The study concludes that addressing jungle justice requires multidimensional, community-based interventions that strengthen justice institutions, restore public trust, and promote social equity.

Keywords: Jungle justice, Ibadan Metropolis, mob violence, self-help theory, structural functionalism, justice system, Nigeria

1. Introduction

Jungle justice, also referred to as mob justice or summary execution, denotes the extrajudicial punishment of alleged offenders by groups or communities without recourse to due process. Ignatius and Nkemjika (2020) describe it as a primitive and emotionally charged response to crime, rooted in deep-seated distrust in formal justice institutions. Ndukwe (2023) and Esara, Etim, and Obong (2024) trace its origin to pre-modern African societies where communal enforcement mechanisms functioned as instruments of social control before the emergence of formal state structures. Obarisiagbon (2018) characterises jungle justice as both a social malady and a modern menace—an enduring manifestation of institutional failure, corruption, and citizens' loss of faith in the rule of law.

The persistence of jungle justice illustrates the tension between the social contract and the failure of the state to uphold its fundamental obligation to protect life and property. According to social contract theorists such as Hobbes (1651), Locke (1689), and Rousseau (1762), citizens surrender certain freedoms to the state in exchange for protection and justice. When the state fails to fulfil these responsibilities, individuals may resort to self-help mechanisms as a means of restoring order. The failed state theory (Helman & Ratner, 1992) reinforces this notion, asserting that states that cannot safeguard citizens' rights or enforce laws equitably risk dysfunction and the erosion of legitimacy.

Globally, jungle justice manifests in diverse forms. In the United States, it is often intertwined with racial violence and police brutality (Butler, 2018); in Canada, it appears in the systemic marginalisation of Indigenous and minority populations (Belanger, 2020); and in the Philippines, it reflects a legacy of colonial-era extrajudicial violence (Hedman, 2017). Across sub-Saharan Africa, jungle justice thrives amid weak governance, judicial inefficiency, and widening socio-economic inequalities. Ernest (2014) and NOI Polls (2014) reveal that Nigeria ranks among the highest globally in incidents of mob justice, with nearly 94% of respondents acknowledging its prevalence.

Existing Nigerian scholarship has explored the moral, legal, and historical dimensions of the phenomenon. Esara *et al.* (2024) highlight its pre-colonial origins as a communal system of enforcement, while Akan (2023) controversially frames it as an informal deterrent to criminal behaviour. Obarisiagbon (2018) links it to endemic corruption and inefficiency in policing, and Kolawole-Amao (2020) conceptualises it as a breach of constitutional order and human rights. Virginus (2022) condemns it from a theological perspective, invoking the biblical principle of due process and the sanctity of life.

Despite these contributions, there remains a paucity of research on the management of jungle justice particularly on how state and non-state actors respond to its challenges within specific urban contexts such as Ibadan Metropolis. Media reports (Sahara Reporters, 2021; Tribune, 2021; Channels Television, 2022; Punch, 2020) document recurring incidents of mob lynching in Ibadan, often arising from economic hardship, public frustration, and the deepening mistrust between citizens and law enforcement agencies.

Against this background, the present study investigates the management of the challenges of jungle justice in Ibadan Metropolis, Oyo State, Nigeria. Specifically, it seeks to: (1) identify the key drivers of jungle justice; (2) examine the challenges encountered by law enforcement and community actors in addressing it; and (3) assess the strategies currently employed to manage and prevent its recurrence. By exploring these dimensions, the study contributes to the broader criminological discourse on governance, community justice, and institutional reform in Nigeria.

Conceptual Clarification

Jungle Justice

Jungle justice refers to the extrajudicial punishment or execution of alleged offenders by a mob without recourse to formal legal institutions. Osaibo (2019) describes it as the public humiliation, assault, or killing of a suspected criminal by an angry crowd, while Kapae and Adishi (2017) define it as a disregard for the rule of law in which individuals take justice into their own hands rather than relying on state authorities. Abdulah (2016) interprets it as the usurpation of the state's responsibility to investigate and punish offenders, and Virginus (2022) emphasises its arbitrary and impulsive nature, often carried out without credible evidence or due process.

Drawing from these perspectives, this study conceptualises jungle justice as an unlawful, emotion-driven, and extra-judicial act in which citizens motivated by anger, fear, or frustration inflict punishment on alleged offenders outside the framework of legal authority. It reflects a profound breakdown of public confidence in formal justice systems and a resort to self-help practices that erode the rule of law, human rights, and social stability.

Challenges

Alemika (2013) defines challenges as obstacles that require effort, innovation, and resilience to overcome, while the Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary (10th ed.) describes a challenge as any situation that makes achieving an objective difficult. Within this study, challenges refer to the structural, institutional, and societal constraints that hinder the effective management of jungle justice in Ibadan Metropolis. These include weak institutional capacity, inadequate funding and logistics for law enforcement, limited community trust in state institutions, and the

slow pace of legal proceedings—all of which collectively undermine the prevention and control of mob action.

Management

Management generally refers to the process of planning, organising, coordinating, and controlling resources to achieve specific objectives effectively and efficiently. Ogundiya (2017) defines it as the act of directing and controlling situations or people, while Kaehler and Grundei (2019) describe it as the strategic coordination of human and material resources to achieve organisational goals. In this study, management encompasses the deliberate efforts, strategies, and policies implemented by state institutions particularly the Nigerian criminal justice system—to curb and prevent jungle justice. It also includes community-based interventions such as public education, advocacy, and collaboration with traditional and religious leaders to promote lawful behaviour, restore trust in the justice system, and strengthen social order.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Although extensive research has examined jungle justice across Nigeria, few studies have explored its dynamics and management within the Ibadan Metropolis, Oyo State. This review synthesises existing literature to identify the causes, effects, and challenges of jungle justice, highlighting the gaps that this study addresses.

Causes of Jungle Justice

The emergence of jungle justice in Nigeria is multifaceted, shaped by historical, institutional, and socio-economic factors. Onwuatuegwu and Nwagu (2020) observe that the practice arises from a convergence of social, political, and psychological elements rather than a single cause. Scholars such as Osaibo (2019) and Kapae and Adishi (2017) attribute its prevalence to declining public trust in formal justice systems. When citizens lose faith in law enforcement and judicial institutions, they resort to mob action as an alternative means of securing justice.

Corruption and institutional decay have been identified as central drivers. Ndukwe (2023) and Brunt (2017) note that systemic corruption and selective enforcement of laws compel citizens to assume the state's punitive role. Illah, Hassan, and Douglas (2022) add that pervasive police corruption undermines due process, reinforcing citizens' perception that justice is only available to the privileged. Bello (2019) similarly links mob justice to Nigeria's history of authoritarianism, which normalised extrajudicial violence and impunity.

Socio-economic inequalities further exacerbate the phenomenon. Kodah (2012) and Orock (2014) identify poverty, unemployment, and illiteracy as major contributors to mob violence, particularly among marginalised groups alienated from state protection. Dambazau (1999) argues

that sustained injustice and class oppression deepen citizens' resentment, while Robert and Greene (1978) highlight inequality as a structural foundation for social unrest.

Judicial inefficiency also sustains jungle justice. Asare (2007) and Neequaye (2007) emphasise that repeated adjournments and prolonged trials undermine confidence in the courts, giving rise to the popular maxim that "justice delayed is justice denied." In such contexts, citizens perceive instant retribution as a corrective measure. Religious intolerance compounds the issue. Ossai (2022) notes that fanaticism and faith-based manipulation have fueled violent mob responses, particularly in blasphemy-related cases such as the killing of Deborah Samuel in Sokoto.

Overall, existing studies demonstrate that jungle justice persists due to weak institutions, corruption, poverty, judicial inefficiency, and social frustration. However, limited attention has been paid to how these dynamics manifest within specific urban contexts like Ibadan, where rapid urbanisation and cultural heterogeneity intensify social tension.

Effects of Jungle Justice

The consequences of jungle justice extend beyond individual acts of violence, posing systemic threats to justice and governance. Adu-Gyamfi (2014) observes that it undermines the credibility of the criminal justice system by portraying state institutions as incapable of protecting citizens. Luke (2013) and Olalekan (2017) warn that mob actions often result in the death of innocent people due to mistaken identity or false accusations, further eroding faith in the rule of law. Beyond human rights violations, jungle justice obstructs criminal investigations by destroying evidence and silencing suspects who might reveal broader criminal networks (Olalekan, 2017). Teju (2012) notes that this perpetuates cycles of vengeance, with affected families and communities seeking retribution, thereby escalating social instability. Ndukwe (2023) further argues that mob justice weakens national cohesion, fosters insecurity, and promotes a culture of anarchy, as it replaces institutional justice with spontaneous violence.

By bypassing legal processes, jungle justice not only denies suspects fair hearing and rehabilitation but also delegitimises the state's monopoly over lawful coercion. It corrodes the justice system, encourages impunity, and perpetuates fear and disorder. Despite these insights, few studies have examined how law enforcement agencies and communities attempt to manage or mitigate the practice, especially in metropolitan contexts such as Ibadan.

Challenges of Jungle Justice

Jungle justice poses significant challenges to Nigeria's criminal justice architecture. Alemika (2013) and Ogundele (2017) argue that it undermines the rule of law by replacing institutional justice with mob-sanctioned violence. Amnesty International (2019) identifies it as a gross violation of human rights, as victims are denied fair trial, legal representation, and the presumption of innocence. Nwankwo (2015) similarly highlights the prevalence of mob convictions based on hearsay, leading to wrongful executions and widespread fear.

Akinlabi (2016) observes that jungle justice perpetuates a culture of vigilantism and retribution, normalising violence as an acceptable means of social control. Igbo (2018) contends that it weakens law enforcement legitimacy, encourages impunity, and obstructs social reintegration of offenders. Furthermore, Ogundele (2017) links its persistence to poverty, unemployment, and inequality conditions that heighten frustration and alienation among the urban poor. Nwankwo (2015) adds that traditional beliefs and community norms sometimes justify mob justice as a culturally legitimate means of deterrence, sustaining harmful practices that challenge formal justice institutions. In essence, the persistence of jungle justice reflects deep moral decay and systemic governance failure. It signals the collapse of institutional trust, where citizens perceive state mechanisms as incapable of guaranteeing justice, thereby resorting to self-help mechanisms that erode legal order and social cohesion.

Managing the Challenges of Jungle Justice

Scholars have proposed multidimensional approaches to curbing the persistence of jungle justice in Nigeria, emphasising the interplay between institutional reform, socio-economic empowerment, and community engagement. Ogundele (2017) identifies poverty alleviation, job creation, and social inclusion as essential measures for addressing the structural roots of mob violence. By improving living standards and providing legitimate economic opportunities, citizens are less likely to channel frustration through extrajudicial means.

Institutional reforms remain central to effective prevention. Akinlabi (2016) and Alemika (2013) underscore the need to strengthen the criminal justice system through prompt investigation, fair prosecution, and credible punishment of offenders. A transparent and responsive judiciary capable of delivering justice without undue delay can help restore public confidence and diminish the perceived need for self-help. Alemika (2013) further advocates the establishment of specialized task forces dedicated to investigating and prosecuting mob-related crimes, thereby enhancing deterrence and institutional accountability. At the community level, restorative justice mechanisms offer complementary pathways to conflict resolution. Nwankwo

(2015) and Igbo (2018) argue for the adoption of community-based mediation and reconciliation programs that prioritise dialogue, restitution, and peacebuilding over retribution. Such initiatives promote social cohesion and reduce the likelihood of spontaneous mob actions.

Public enlightenment and civic education also constitutes a vital strategy. According to Igbo (2018) and Ogundele (2017), sustained sensitisation through mass media, schools, and religious institutions can reshape public attitudes toward justice and human rights. Engaging traditional rulers, faith leaders, and community organisations as partners in advocacy can further strengthen collaboration between citizens and law enforcement agencies.

Accordingly, managing jungle justice requires a coordinated, multi-stakeholder strategy that integrates legal reform, socio-economic empowerment, and community participation. Rebuilding trust in the justice system and addressing underlying socio-economic grievances are indispensable for eradicating this persistent form of extrajudicial violence in Nigeria.

Theoretical Framework

This study draws on **Structural Functionalism Theory** and **Self-Help Theory** to explain the persistence of jungle justice in Nigeria. Together, these frameworks illuminate how institutional dysfunction and citizens' adaptive responses to systemic failure shape the rise of informal mechanisms of justice within society.

Structural Functionalism Theory

Structural Functionalism, originally advanced by Herbert Spencer (1867) and later developed by Émile Durkheim (1895) and Talcott Parsons (1951), conceptualises society as an interdependent system composed of institutions—such as the family, economy, religion, and judiciary each performing distinct functions that maintain social equilibrium. When one institution fails to perform effectively, dysfunction emerges, threatening overall stability and leading to deviant or compensatory social behaviour.

In the Nigerian context, the criminal justice system comprising the police, judiciary, and correctional services constitutes a critical structural component. Persistent inefficiencies, corruption, and judicial delays represent institutional dysfunctions that undermine the state's capacity to enforce the rule of law. These failures erode citizens' confidence in formal justice processes and generate conditions under which alternative, informal systems of justice, such as mob action, become normalised.

The link between structural functionalism and jungle justice lies in the breakdown of institutional performance. When formal mechanisms for maintaining social order collapse, communities attempt to restore equilibrium through informal and extra-legal means. Jungle justice, though unlawful, functions as a substitute system of social regulation an attempt by

citizens to reassert communal norms and punish deviance in the absence of effective state intervention.

However, structural functionalism has been critiqued for overemphasising stability and consensus while neglecting inequality, conflict, and power relations. It tends to assume that social institutions are inherently beneficial, overlooking how corruption, oppression, and social injustice contribute to dysfunction. Despite these limitations, the theory remains useful for this study as it explains how institutional breakdown within the Nigerian justice system has created the structural conditions that allow jungle justice to persist.

Self-Help Theory

The Self-Help Theory, developed by Donald Black (1983), posits that when individuals or groups perceive formal legal systems as inaccessible, corrupt, or ineffective, they resort to unilateral action to address perceived wrongs. Such self-help behaviour represents a breakdown of state-controlled social order, whereby individuals assume direct responsibility for enforcing norms and dispensing justice. It emerges as a response to legal failure, manifesting in both individual and collective forms of retaliation.

Self-Help Theory provides critical behavioural insight into the persistence of jungle justice in Nigeria. In Ibadan Metropolis, many citizens perceive the formal justice system as slow, corrupt, and biased in favour of the wealthy and politically connected. Consequently, they engage in mob action as a form of immediate retribution an act of communal self-help intended to restore moral order and deterrence. Jungle justice thus becomes the extreme and violent expression of self-help, reflecting both frustration with systemic inefficiency and a collective search for justice outside legal institutions.

Nevertheless, the theory has been criticised for inadvertently legitimising violence by framing it as a rational reaction to state failure. It overlooks the potential for constructive self-help through non-violent community action, such as mediation, advocacy, and civic education. In contexts where legal institutions are weak, non-state actors including human rights organisations, traditional authorities, and faith-based groups can channel self-help impulses toward restorative and lawful solutions.

Taken together, Structural Functionalism and Self-Help Theory provide a comprehensive lens for understanding jungle justice. Structural Functionalism situates the phenomenon within systemic dysfunction emphasising institutional breakdown and social disequilibrium while Self-Help Theory explains the behavioural response to that dysfunction, where citizens assume justice functions that the state fails to perform. Through this dual framework, jungle justice is

understood both as a symptom of structural decay and as a socially constructed, though unlawful, attempt to restore order in a context of institutional failure.

Methodology

This study adopted a qualitative case study design to explore the management of the challenges of jungle justice in Ibadan Metropolis, Oyo State, Nigeria. The qualitative approach was chosen because it provides rich, contextual insights into complex social phenomena by capturing participants' lived experiences and interpretations. As Priya (2021) observes, case study research enables an in-depth understanding of real-life issues within their social and institutional contexts. Given the study's focus on the causes, challenges, and management of jungle justice, this design offered an appropriate framework for generating descriptive and interpretive data from multiple perspectives.

The research was conducted in Ibadan Metropolis, the capital of Oyo State and Nigeria's third-largest city after Lagos and Kano. Ibadan comprises eleven Local Government Areas: Egbeda, Ibadan North, Akinyele, Ibadan North East, Ibadan North West, Ibadan South East, Ibadan South West, Ido, Lagelu, Oluyole, and Ona Ara with an estimated population of 4.1 million people and a land area of 3,080 square kilometres (Macrotrends, 2025). The metropolis was purposively selected because of its recurrent incidents of mob-related violence, as documented by media and human rights reports, making it an ideal setting for studying the persistence and management of jungle justice in an urban Nigerian context.

The study population comprised residents of Ibadan Metropolis with firsthand or professional experience related to jungle justice. Participants were selected across key sectors, including human rights advocacy, academia, religious institutions, community leadership, and youth activism. The study employed purposive sampling to ensure that participants possessed relevant knowledge and could provide insightful contributions. As Stratton (2024) notes, purposive sampling is particularly effective in qualitative inquiries because it engages information-rich participants who can offer contextually grounded perspectives. A total of nine participants were interviewed: two human rights lawyers, one representative of a human rights organisation, one university scholar in security studies, two community leaders, one youth activist, one Christian religious leader, and one Muslim religious leader. This diversity of respondents allowed for triangulation of views from both institutional and community standpoints.

Data collection relied primarily on in-depth interviews (IDIs) and key informant interviews (KIIs). A semi-structured interview guide was developed in line with the study's objectives, containing open-ended questions that encouraged participants to share their

experiences and perceptions freely. Interviews were conducted in English, recorded with participants' consent using a digital voice recorder, and lasted between forty-five and sixty minutes depending on participants' availability and engagement. In addition to primary data, secondary sources such as books, peer-reviewed journal articles, policy documents, and media reports were reviewed. These materials provided contextual background and supported the triangulation of findings, thereby enhancing the credibility and dependability of the study.

The collected data were analysed thematically. Interview recordings were transcribed verbatim, and the transcripts were coded manually to identify recurring patterns, ideas, and themes. Thematic analysis enabled the identification of relationships among concepts and the interpretation of participants' narratives within the study's theoretical framework. The analysis was both descriptive and interpretive, highlighting how individual and institutional experiences intersect to shape perceptions of jungle justice and its management.

Ethical considerations were strictly observed throughout the research process. All participants were fully informed about the purpose of the study, their voluntary participation, and their right to withdraw at any stage without consequence. Informed consent either written or verbal was obtained from each participant before interviews commenced. To ensure confidentiality, pseudonyms or professional titles (for example, "Respondent 2 – Human Rights Lawyer") were used instead of real names, consistent with Itzik and Walsh's (2023) recommendation that pseudonyms protect participant anonymity in qualitative studies. Participants who preferred to have their real names disclosed were respected in accordance with their consent. All data collected were used solely for academic purposes, and no sensitive personal information was made public.

Some challenges were encountered during fieldwork, including limited access to official data from the Nigeria Police Force due to bureaucratic restrictions, which constrained institutional perspectives. To mitigate this, secondary data and insights from human rights advocates and community leaders were incorporated. Although a planned focus group discussion could not be conducted due to scheduling conflicts, the depth and consistency of individual interviews provided robust and reliable data.

Overall, the methodological approach employed in this study facilitated a comprehensive exploration of how jungle justice is perceived, managed, and challenged in Ibadan Metropolis. The combination of qualitative design, purposive sampling, and thematic analysis yielded a holistic understanding of the phenomenon while maintaining the ethical integrity and methodological rigour required for scholarly research.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

DRIVERS OF JUNGLE JUSTICE IN IBADAN METROPOLIS

The study identified multiple, interrelated factors driving the persistence of jungle justice in Ibadan Metropolis, including economic hardship, social dislocation, distrust in justice institutions, weak law enforcement, political manipulation, unemployment, moral decline, and the broader failure of the state.

Economic Factors

Across interviews, participants consistently cited poverty and economic hardship as key triggers of mob violence. Comrade Alabi Oyetunde, Executive Director of the Mediation Conciliation and Human Rights Center, stated: “Economic hardship and poverty are the causes of jungle justice. People are struggling to survive; when someone steals even a little, the anger from daily suffering fuels mob violence.” (IDI, 18 March 2025). Similarly, Mr. Rufus Olajide, Head of Chambers at The Law Hub, emphasised that pervasive deprivation heightens aggression and makes people more prone to violent reactions. These findings align with Kodah (2012) and Orock (2014), who link economic inequality and unemployment to social frustration and violent self-help actions.

Social and Cultural Factors

Respondents highlighted declining moral values, weak family structures, and limited civic education as significant enablers of jungle justice. Mr. Olajide observed that “many perpetrators were not taught to value human life,” while Pastor Isaac Olawole attributed mob behavior to “ignorance of the law and its consequences.” This moral and social breakdown supports Structural Functionalism’s assertion that when socialisation agents such as families, schools, and religious institutions fail to transmit civic norms, deviant behaviour emerges to fill the vacuum.

Political and Leadership Factors

Political manipulation and leadership failure were also identified as contributors. Mr. Olajide recounted that some politicians “hire people to accuse opponents and lead their execution through jungle justice.” (IDI, 21 March 2025). Such political weaponisation of mob action reflects the erosion of institutional integrity. Pastor Olawole added that “corruption and poor governance breed public frustration and distrust,” echoing Udo’s (2022) argument that corrupt leadership perpetuates impunity and weakens formal justice systems.

Distrust in the Justice System

A recurring theme among respondents was deep-seated distrust in Nigeria’s judicial processes. Delayed trials, corruption, and selective enforcement have eroded confidence in the courts. According to Comrade Oyetunde, “People would rather mete out justice themselves than wait for

the long judicial process. Our courts are slow justice delayed is justice denied.” (IDI, 18 March 2025). This perception reflects the Self-Help Theory’s argument that when institutional trust collapses, citizens resort to informal justice mechanisms to restore perceived fairness.

Perceived Ineffectiveness of Law Enforcement

Participants consistently described the police as compromised, under-resourced, and untrustworthy. Comrade Oyetunde noted that offenders often “bribe their way out of custody,” while Mr. Olajide lamented “shoddy investigations and unlawful releases.” Such institutional weaknesses reinforce citizens’ preference for instant justice, as also observed by Illah, Hassan, and Douglas (2022), who link police corruption to the normalisation of mob action.

Failure of the State

The findings reveal a broader structural failure of the Nigerian state to uphold citizens’ rights and security. Human rights lawyer Mr. Adebajji Adesoji explained that: “A failed state is one that cannot provide security or protect citizens’ rights. When these rights—life, fair hearing, and legal representation are denied, people resort to jungle justice.” (IDI, 24 March 2025). This view aligns with the Failed-State Thesis and the Self-Help Theory, both of which posit that systemic dysfunction leads citizens to construct their own mechanisms of justice.

Religious and Moral Factors

Moral decay and declining spirituality were also identified as enablers of jungle justice. Pastor Olawole emphasised that “if more people feared God, they would obey the law instead of committing jungle justice,” while Alfa Sulaimon Abdulrasaq added that Islam enjoins peace and due process, but “people disregard divine commandments out of anger and ignorance.” The Baale of Oba Oluyole, Yemi Ogunyemi, lamented that “the absence of fear of God has eroded societal restraint.” These views highlight religion’s potential role in reinforcing lawful conduct and moral discipline.

Unemployment and Rural–Urban Migration

Finally, respondents connected jungle justice to widespread unemployment and the influx of idle youth into the city. Community leader Mr. Raufu Adeoye observed: “Unemployment is one of the main causes of jungle justice. An idle mind is the devil’s workshop; jobless youths are quick to join any mob shouting ‘thief!’” (KII, 23 April 2025). Rural migrants who fail to secure livelihoods often become frustrated and vulnerable to mob participation. This supports Akinlabi’s (2016) view that economic dislocation and youth unemployment are strong predictors of communal violence.

CHALLENGES ASSOCIATED WITH THE MANAGEMENT OF JUNGLE JUSTICE IN IBADAN METROPOLIS

Despite several initiatives, managing jungle justice in Ibadan remains constrained by structural, institutional, and social challenges. Key issues identified include the overpowering of law enforcement by mobs, difficulty verifying allegations, and inadequate funding of justice institutions.

Public Overpowering of Law Enforcement

Respondents emphasised that police officers are frequently overwhelmed by mobs during incidents of jungle justice. Comrade Oyetunde explained: “The people are difficult to control; even community leaders and police officers struggle to stop them. There have been cases where policemen trying to calm mobs were beaten or killed because people believed they were rescuing the offender.” (IDI, 18 March 2025). This finding reflects Ogundele’s (2017) assertion that mob resistance to law enforcement erodes state authority and weakens social order.

Difficulty in Verifying Allegations

False accusations and rumor-driven violence emerged as critical obstacles. Mr. Olajide recounted a case where a man “was nearly beaten to death for allegedly stealing another person’s penis” before police intervention revealed his innocence (IDI, 21 March 2025). Such incidents underscore how misinformation and superstition compromise justice. This aligns with Nwankwo (2015) and Akinlabi (2016), who identify weak investigative capacity and low legal literacy as barriers to effective mob control.

Inadequate Funding and Poor Resource Allocation

Participants also cited chronic underfunding of law enforcement agencies as a core institutional weakness. Professor Isaac Albert explained: “We often accuse security agencies of corruption, but they are underequipped and lack motivation. In many cases, criminals are better armed than the police.” (KII, 23 April 2025). As Akinyemi and Chukwuma (2024) argue, limited resources constrain the police’s ability to respond promptly, investigate thoroughly, or prosecute effectively, allowing mob justice to thrive unchallenged.

MANAGING THE CHALLENGES OF JUNGLE JUSTICE IN IBADAN METROPOLIS

Findings revealed that the management of jungle justice in Ibadan relies on four main strategies: public enlightenment, promotion of equity and fairness, job creation, and improved education.

Public Enlightenment and Awareness

Public education emerged as the most common strategy for curbing jungle justice. According to Comrade Oyetunde: “One of the strategies the government uses is public enlightenment through radio, television, newspapers, and other media. Agencies like the National Orientation Agency

and the Ministry of Information also engage religious and community platforms.” (IDI, 18 March 2025). Although respondents agreed that these campaigns have limited reach, they remain crucial for reshaping perceptions and encouraging lawful conflict resolution. This finding supports Igbo’s (2018) argument that sustained civic education can gradually reduce extrajudicial violence.

Promoting Equity and Fairness

Perceptions of inequality in justice delivery fuel mob action. Community leader Mr. Raufu Adeoye noted: “If the government promotes equity and fairness in our justice system, people would have no reason to take the law into their own hands.” (KII, 23 April 2025). This reinforces Ogundele’s (2017) position that transparent and impartial judicial processes are essential for restoring public trust.

Providing Job Opportunities

Respondents consistently emphasised employment creation as a preventive measure. Mr. Adeoye stated that “providing more job opportunities would reduce idleness and help curb jungle justice” (KII, 23 April 2025). Employment, as Akinlabi (2016) suggests, reduces frustration and channels youth energy toward productive engagement.

Proper Education and Civic Orientation

Finally, respondents emphasised education as a long-term solution. Mr. Adeoye observed that “proper education reshapes people’s mindsets and makes society more civilised” (KII, 23 April 2025). Educational initiatives promoting civic responsibility, human rights, and legal literacy can foster a more law-abiding citizenry, aligning with Alemika’s (2013) assertion that civic education strengthens societal order and institutional legitimacy.

The study establishes that jungle justice in Ibadan is sustained by intertwined socio-economic, institutional, and moral factors. Its persistence reflects systemic distrust in governance and justice mechanisms. Managing this phenomenon requires a holistic approach that combines structural reforms, socio-economic empowerment, and community-based enlightenment to rebuild public confidence in the rule of law.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

DRIVERS OF JUNGLE JUSTICE IN IBADAN METROPOLIS, OYO STATE

The study examined the underlying factors driving jungle justice in Ibadan Metropolis, drawing on data from in-depth (IDI) and key informant interviews (KII). Findings reveal that the practice is sustained by a convergence of economic hardship, social dislocation, political manipulation, and a widespread loss of faith in the formal justice system. These results reinforce existing scholarship while offering context-specific insights into the Ibadan environment.

Economic and Social Factors

Economic deprivation and unemployment were consistently identified as major triggers of mob justice. Respondents emphasised that the worsening economic situation has heightened public frustration and intolerance, making people quick to resort to violence when confronting alleged offenders. One respondent remarked that *“if a person is caught stealing even a small item, people react violently because of their own struggles with hardship.”* This aligns with Mahachi (2025) and Kodah (2012), who identify poverty and unemployment as structural enablers of jungle justice. Within the framework of **Self-Help Theory** (Black, 1983), such behaviour illustrates how citizens, frustrated by the state’s inability to deliver justice or economic security, resort to self-enforced measures to achieve retribution. As institutional reliability erodes, informal mechanisms such as mob action emerge as substitutes for state authority.

Social ignorance and weak moral foundations further compounding this reality. Respondents linked jungle justice to widespread legal illiteracy and declining family values, with many perpetrators unaware that their actions constitute criminal offenses. This finding supports Blueprint (2023) and Muhammad (2025), who argue that ignorance of legal processes and the normalisation of mob punishment perpetuate extrajudicial behavior. The family, which Gittins (1993) describes as the primary agent of socialisation, plays a vital role in instilling civic virtues such as empathy, accountability, and respect for the law. When this function fails, individuals become more susceptible to impulsive violence, validating the Self-Help Theory’s contention that people fill the void left by failing institutions through their own, often unlawful, interventions.

Political Factors

Political manipulation and poor governance also emerged as key drivers. Respondents recounted incidents where political actors allegedly mobilised mobs against rivals by spreading false accusations. As one noted, *“Political rivals sometimes frame opponents for crimes and lead the mob that executes them.”* This finding echoes Luxman (2024), who contends that corruption and personal interests within Nigeria’s political system undermine institutional trust and normalise violence. Similarly, Brodowicz (2024) links political rivalry to heightened insecurity and the erosion of the rule of law.

According to Chukwudi et al. (2025), jungle justice can also be weaponised for political gain, transforming from a spontaneous act of communal anger into a deliberate instrument of intimidation. From a Self-Help Theory perspective, such dynamics reveal how the breakdown of political integrity leads citizens to view justice as a personal or collective responsibility rather

than a state function. As Smith and Porter (2022) observe, when governance fails, informal systems of justice emerge to fill the resulting vacuum.

Lack of Trust in the Formal Justice System

Perhaps the most pervasive finding is the erosion of public confidence in the judiciary and law enforcement institutions. Respondents repeatedly described the justice system as corrupt, slow, and biased. One participant stated that *“people would rather mete out justice themselves than wait for endless court adjournments—justice delayed is justice denied.”* This sentiment resonates with Dada et al. (2015) and Agbibo (2015), who argue that judicial inefficiency and corruption encourage citizens to bypass formal processes in favour of mob justice.

Illah et al. (2022) further contend that systemic corruption within the judiciary creates a perception that certain individuals are “above the law,” reinforcing public cynicism. This aligns with Self-Help Theory, which posits that citizens resort to unilateral actions when institutional justice mechanisms are inaccessible or untrustworthy. However, one respondent, Mr. Rufus Olajide, offered a nuanced view, arguing that impatience and misunderstanding of legal processes often fuel mob behaviour. He noted that judicial procedures must balance efficiency with accuracy and uphold the constitutional presumption of innocence under Section 36(5) of the 1999 Constitution. This perspective echoes Babatunde (2003), who warns that jungle justice violates the right to fair hearing and risks punishing the innocent highlighting one of the central moral and legal contradictions of self-help justice.

The findings suggest that jungle justice in Ibadan is not merely an expression of anger but a complex social response to institutional dysfunction and economic despair. The Self-Help Theory provides a coherent framework for interpreting these dynamics: when citizens perceive the state as weak, unjust, or corrupt, they reclaim the authority to enforce justice themselves. Yet, this self-enforcement undermines the very legal order it seeks to restore.

The persistence of jungle justice thus reveals a paradox a society demanding justice through injustice. Addressing this phenomenon requires more than legal reform; it demands structural interventions that rebuild economic stability, restore faith in governance, and re-establish the legitimacy of formal justice institutions.

Endemic Corruption of Law Enforcement Agencies

Corruption within law enforcement emerged as one of the strongest drivers of jungle justice in Ibadan. Respondents consistently emphasised that police corruption undermines public confidence in the justice system and encourages citizens to pursue extrajudicial alternatives. As one participant explained, *“People believe that the police will release offenders once they bribe them. They often see those same offenders back in their communities, unpunished.”* This

perception reflects broader systemic dysfunction. Ordu (2015) identifies corruption, delayed justice delivery, and professional misconduct as major impediments to effective policing in Nigeria. Empirical evidence from the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC, 2019) corroborates this, revealing that police officers account for more than one-third (35.7%) of all bribes paid nationwide. Similarly, another respondent noted that “the police often collect bribes and release suspects unlawfully after poorly conducted investigations.”

As Nwocha (2024) and Akuul (2011) observe, the police remain the most visible arm of law enforcement in Nigeria, tasked with preventing crime, protecting lives, and upholding public order. When these duties are compromised by corruption or incompetence, citizens’ trust in formal mechanisms deteriorates. This validates the Self-Help Theory (Black, 1983), which posits that when institutional systems of justice fail, individuals and communities adopt informal or unilateral measures to enforce perceived fairness. Corruption within law enforcement therefore does not merely erode legitimacy it directly fuels jungle justice by pushing citizens to become enforcers of their own version of justice.

Failure of the State

The findings also reveal that jungle justice in Ibadan is symptomatic of a broader crisis of governance. Respondents described it as a consequence of state incapacity to protect citizens and enforce the rule of law. A human rights lawyer summarised this position succinctly: “*A failed state is one that cannot provide basic security or protect citizens’ rights. When these rights are violated without consequence, people resort to jungle justice.*” This observation aligns with Chukwudi et al. (2025), who argue that mob justice proliferates when the state abdicates its responsibility to guarantee justice and equality before the law. Amnesty International (2024) likewise contends that the Nigerian government’s failure to investigate and prosecute offenders has emboldened citizens to take the law into their own hands.

Scholars such as Sobczynski (2019), Qualls (2022), and ISE (2023) emphasise that the essential functions of the state security, governance, and protection of rights are foundational to maintaining social order. When these collapse, citizens instinctively fill the vacuum through informal and often violent justice mechanisms. Within the logic of Self-Help Theory, this represents the point at which collective frustration becomes a catalyst for social disorder. Mob action, while unlawful, is seen as compensatory a means of restoring order in the perceived absence of a functioning state.

Lack of Faithful Leadership

Poor leadership and political corruption were also identified as central to the persistence of jungle justice. Respondents associated bad governance with weak law enforcement, selective

justice, and rising public anger. As one religious leader remarked, “*The issue of jungle justice is a result of bad leadership. People see the government as corrupt and prefer to take justice into their own hands because they believe it is faster and less corrupt.*” This corroborates Anazodo et al. (2015), who argue that unaccountable leadership erodes the rule of law and fosters impunity. Udo (2022) similarly links weak governance to the normalisation of illegal practices such as mob violence.

In contrast, Barney and Pratt (2023) define leadership as the ethical capacity to guide and influence society toward lawful goals. When leaders fail to embody justice and integrity, citizens lose trust in public institutions and revert to self-help justice. This dynamic again reinforces Black’s (1983) argument that institutional collapse shifts the burden of justice enforcement onto individuals and communities.

Moral and Religious Decline

Moral decay and declining spirituality were also recurrent themes in the data. Religious leaders interviewed emphasised that the loss of moral restraint contributes significantly to mob violence. A Christian cleric noted, “*The Bible teaches peace and obedience to authority, but people disregard these teachings and act in ways that displease God.*” Likewise, a Muslim leader asserted that “the Qur’an enjoins believers to uphold justice and due process; jungle justice is a sin before Allah.” Sochor (2014) attributes many societal problems to the absence of the fear of God, while AIMS Education (2025) points to Qur’anic injunctions such as *Surah Al-Ahzab 33:36* and *Surah An-Nisa 4:60*, which emphasise obedience to lawful authority.

Oladimeji (2024) also underscores the role of religion in promoting compassion, forgiveness, and respect for the rule of law. When religious and moral teachings lose their influence, individuals become desensitised to violence and more willing to participate in mob actions. This moral vacuum reflects a social dimension of Self-Help Theory when both legal and moral institutions weaken, citizens rely on unregulated mechanisms to resolve grievances.

Unemployment

Unemployment was repeatedly cited as a structural driver of jungle justice. Respondents described joblessness as a catalyst for frustration and deviant behaviour. One community leader observed, “*It is only jobless people who stop to join a mob. If people were employed, they wouldn’t have the time or energy for jungle justice.*” This perspective supports Brodowicz (2024) and Umar et al. (2025), who argue that unemployment intensifies crime rates and social unrest, creating fertile ground for mob violence.

Similarly, Obasanjo et al. (2023) link unemployment to economic despair and weakened civic order. While the anonymity of mob participants makes direct verification difficult, the

correlation between economic inactivity and participation in extrajudicial acts remains strong. Lack of employment diminishes social responsibility and increases susceptibility to impulsive, collective violence.

Rural–Urban Migration

Rural–urban migration further compounds the problem by exacerbating unemployment and urban poverty. Okegbe and Okechukwu (2024) define the process as the movement of people from rural to urban areas in search of better opportunities, while Ikezue (2023) notes that this often results in overcrowding and increased crime in cities with limited infrastructure. A community leader in Ibadan explained that *“many rural migrants do not find greener pastures in the city; they end up roaming joblessly, looking for ways to survive, which sometimes leads to crime.”*

This finding indicates that migration-induced dislocation amplifies social instability and contributes to the rise of mob violence in urban settings. Migrants who fail to integrate economically or socially may become both perpetrators and victims of jungle justice, highlighting the intersection between economic marginalisation and extrajudicial behaviour. Within the Self-Help framework, such individuals alienated from both formal institutions and traditional community structures turn to informal justice mechanisms as substitutes for state protection.

The evidence from Ibadan confirms that jungle justice is a multidimensional phenomenon rooted in structural inequality, institutional decay, and moral decline. The main drivers identified include economic hardship, social disintegration, political manipulation, corruption within law enforcement, state failure, poor leadership, unemployment, and rural–urban migration. These factors interact in complex ways to erode citizens’ confidence in formal justice institutions and reinforce dependence on self-help mechanisms.

The findings are consistent with the works of Kodah (2012), Luxman (2024), Folasade (2023), Nwocha (2024), and Udo (2022), and substantiate Donald Black’s Self-Help Theory (1983), which asserts that when legal systems lose accessibility and credibility, citizens reclaim the responsibility of enforcing justice themselves. Ultimately, the persistence of jungle justice in Ibadan reflects a deeper systemic crisis the weakening of state institutions and the moral foundations that sustain law, order, and justice in society.

CHALLENGES ASSOCIATED WITH THE MANAGEMENT OF JUNGLE JUSTICE IN IBADAN METROPOLIS

Overpowering of the Police by Mobs

A major challenge identified in managing jungle justice in Ibadan is the frequent overpowering of law enforcement officers by enraged mobs. Okafor (2023) observes that police personnel often find themselves incapacitated in such volatile situations, as deep-seated public aggression and the entrenched culture of self-help prevent effective intervention. This finding aligns with the Self-Help Theory (Black, 1983), which explains that when citizens lose trust in state mechanisms, they assume personal responsibility for enforcing justice.

Equally, respondents in this study confirmed that inadequate manpower, obsolete equipment, and poor response times further constrain the police's ability to manage mob violence (Eze & Okon, 2023). One participant noted that "the people are difficult to control, which makes it extremely hard for community leaders and security agencies to intervene." Another observed that police officers, fearing for their own safety, often delay action until reinforcements arrive by which time the alleged offender is frequently dead.

This recurrent failure undermines public confidence in formal justice processes. As Ogunyemi and Isah (2024) argue, the inability of the police to assert control emboldens communities to rely on vigilante or mob actions. When law enforcement fails to fulfill its statutory duties of crime prevention, investigation, and protection of lives and property (Akuul, 2011), it validates the Self-Help Theory's assertion that distrust in state institutions compels citizens to substitute due process with extrajudicial measures.

Difficulty in Verifying Allegations

Another critical challenge is the difficulty of determining the veracity of accusations before mob action occurs. Nwankwo (2015) observes that jungle justice is often triggered by hearsay, rumour, or circumstantial evidence, resulting in the punishment or death of innocent individuals. This was illustrated by one respondent, who recounted a case where a man was nearly lynched for allegedly "stealing another person's genitals" a claim later proven false after police intervention.

The inability to verify allegations reflects not only procedural weakness but also public impatience and frustration with systemic inefficiency. Socio-economic hardship, corruption, and judicial delay have produced a reactive culture in which citizens replace investigation with immediate retribution. As Folasade (2023) and Brooks (2023) emphasise, the presumption of innocence until proven guilty is central to the rule of law; when law enforcement and the

judiciary fail to uphold this principle, it creates an environment conducive to mob violence. This dynamic reinforces the Self-Help Theory's premise: citizens who perceive formal institutions as biased or ineffectual are more likely to administer justice themselves, often with fatal consequences.

Inadequate Funding and Poor Resource Allocation

Chronic underfunding of the police and other justice institutions also emerged as a major impediment to managing jungle justice effectively. Akinyemi and Chukwuma (2024) and Yusuf and Okafor (2023) contend that financial constraints weaken institutional capacity for crime prevention, investigation, and prosecution. Many police stations in Ibadan reportedly lack essential logistics such as patrol vehicles, communication tools, and forensic facilities limitations that hinder timely intervention during mob incidents.

This concern was echoed by one respondent, who noted that “security agencies are under equipped and often lack motivation to go all out for their jobs; sometimes, criminals are even better armed than the police.” Similarly, Obaro and Musa (2024) argue that low remuneration and poor welfare conditions reduce officer morale and foster corruption, further eroding public trust in law enforcement.

As citizens perceive the police as ineffective or compromised, they resort to self-help strategies such as jungle justice. This creates a vicious cycle: inadequate funding produces inefficiency, inefficiency erodes legitimacy, and eroded legitimacy reinforces reliance on vigilantism. The pattern echoes the Self-Help Theory's central proposition that when state institutions are weak, underfunded, or distrusted, citizens will pursue extralegal means of achieving justice (Okafor, 2023; Okoye, 2023; Obaro & Musa, 2024).

The challenges identified police incapacitation, unverifiable accusations, and resource inadequacy collectively illustrate the structural fragility of Nigeria's criminal justice system. These weaknesses perpetuate a cycle of distrust and retaliation that sustains jungle justice in Ibadan. The findings therefore reaffirm the *Self-Help Theory's* explanatory power in showing how institutional failure, rather than mere public aggression, lies at the heart of extrajudicial violence.

MANAGING THE CHALLENGES OF JUNGLE JUSTICE IN IBADAN METROPOLIS

Public Enlightenment and Awareness

Public enlightenment and awareness campaigns emerged as one of the most effective strategies for curbing jungle justice in Ibadan. Udo and Ibrahim (2023) argue that mob violence persists largely because of widespread ignorance of legal processes, mistrust in state institutions, and weak understanding of human rights. Sustained education and advocacy, therefore, serve as

critical tools for correcting misconceptions and fostering public confidence in lawful justice mechanisms. This finding was supported by Respondent 1, who noted that “one of the strategies the government uses to manage jungle justice is through public enlightenment,” citing agencies such as the National Orientation Agency and the Ministry of Information. Similarly, Adigun and Nwankwo (2024) emphasise community-based sensitisation through local information centres, religious institutions, and marketplaces.

From the perspective of Self-Help Theory (Black, 1983), enlightenment represents a constructive and non-violent form of self-help, empowering citizens to hold institutions accountable through knowledge rather than aggression. Awareness campaigns promote understanding of constitutional rights, the illegality of mob action, and the moral implications of extrajudicial behaviour. Thus, public enlightenment functions both preventively and restoratively addressing the psychological and structural roots of jungle justice by nurturing empathy, civic responsibility, and respect for due process.

Promoting Equity and Fairness

Ensuring equity and fairness within the justice system is fundamental to mitigating jungle justice. Ogunleye and Musa (2024) observe that public perception of bias, corruption, and inaccessibility within formal institutions drives citizens to seek retribution through mob action. Likewise, Chukwu and Balogun (2023) contend that when justice is transparent and impartial, citizens are more inclined to pursue lawful channels of redress.

Respondent 9 affirmed this connection, stating that “if the government promotes equity and fairness in the justice system, people would have no reason to engage in self-help strategies such as jungle justice.” Umeh and Danjuma (2023) similarly call for stronger legal aid services and community-based human rights institutions to ensure fairness and accessibility. This finding resonates with **Structural-Functionalist Theory** (Durkheim, 1895; Parsons, 1951), which emphasises the interdependence of social institutions. When the judiciary, police, and human rights agencies perform their functions equitably, social order and legitimacy are sustained. Conversely, systemic bias or corruption disrupts this equilibrium, compelling citizens to restore “justice” through informal and often violent means.

Proper Education

Education represents a long-term, transformative approach to reducing jungle justice. Adeleke and Mohammed (2024) identify mob violence as a product of ignorance and civic disconnection, arguing that education fosters legal literacy, critical reasoning, and awareness of human rights. Similarly, Ekanem and Lawal (2023) stress that civic and human rights education promote empathy, tolerance, and respect for lawful procedures. This was further echoed by Respondent 9,

who stated that “proper education would mould people’s orientation towards many things, including jungle justice; the society would be more civilised.”

Abubakar and Iheanacho (2024) note that lessons on governance and civic participation enhance citizens’ willingness to rely on legal institutions rather than mob action. From a Structural-Functionalist viewpoint, education serves as a stabilising institution, transmitting social norms and discouraging deviant behaviour. When schools, religious bodies, and community structures fulfil this role effectively, collective adherence to lawful conflict resolution is strengthened, thereby reducing the prevalence of jungle justice.

Providing Job Opportunities

Addressing unemployment is another vital measure in managing the challenges of jungle justice. Okon and Abdulrahman (2024) and Umar et al. (2025) argue that mob justice thrives in contexts of poverty, frustration, and economic exclusion. Employment creation enhances stability, reduces idleness, and restores citizens’ trust in governance. This was reflected in the statement of Respondent 9, who explained that “providing more job opportunities would solve the issue of unemployment and idleness, which would help reduce jungle justice in Ibadan.”

Usman and Eze (2024) similarly observe that individuals with stable livelihoods are more inclined to uphold peace and legality. Within the Structural-Functionalist framework, economic institutions are central to maintaining social equilibrium; when they fail to provide equitable opportunities, deviance and lawlessness tend to rise. Job creation and livelihood improvement, therefore, address both material deprivation and the deeper social alienation that drives mob behaviour.

These strategies public enlightenment, equitable justice, education, and employment demonstrate that managing jungle justice requires a multidimensional, society wide approach. Supported by both the Self-Help Theory and Structural-Functionalist Theory, the findings reveal that reducing mob violence depends not only on institutional reform but also on addressing the social, educational, and economic structures that sustain public frustration and lawlessness. A coordinated response that strengthens state legitimacy, promotes fairness, and empowers citizens through knowledge and opportunity is essential for breaking the cycle of jungle justice in Ibadan Metropolis.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined the dynamics of jungle justice in Ibadan Metropolis, focusing on its underlying drivers, management challenges, and existing strategies for mitigation. Jungle justice, understood as the extrajudicial punishment of alleged offenders by mobs without recourse to due process, remains a critical social and institutional problem in Nigeria. Using a qualitative case

study approach, data were collected through in-depth and key informant interviews with human rights advocates, community leaders, religious figures, legal practitioners, and scholars. The analysis, anchored in the Self-Help Theory and the Structural-Functionalist Theory, provided important insights into both the behavioural motivations behind mob action and the institutional failures that sustain it.

Findings revealed that jungle justice in Ibadan is not merely a consequence of weak law enforcement but a manifestation of deeper systemic decay. Economic hardship, unemployment, ignorance, political rivalry, endemic corruption, and pervasive distrust in the justice system collectively fuel its persistence. When formal institutions fail to deliver justice fairly and promptly, citizens often resort to self-help mechanisms to restore order and moral balance, even at the expense of legality and human rights. The malfunctioning of social institutions such as education, religion, and governance further exacerbates the problem, creating vacuums that informal mechanisms of justice attempt to fill.

Although efforts have been made by both government agencies and civil society to address jungle justice through public enlightenment campaigns, legal reforms, and community-based interventions their impact has been limited by corruption, poor coordination, inadequate funding, and weak grassroots participation. The persistence of mob justice therefore reflects a profound crisis of legitimacy and public confidence in Nigeria's justice and governance systems.

To curb this menace, the study recommends a multidimensional and community-driven approach that combines institutional reform with social empowerment.

Strengthening the criminal justice system through transparent, fair, and expedited trials is crucial to rebuilding public trust. Law enforcement agencies must be adequately funded, trained, and monitored to ensure professionalism and accountability. Public enlightenment campaigns should be sustained and localised through both traditional and digital media to educate citizens about the dangers and illegality of mob action. Traditional and religious leaders should also be integrated into community-level conflict resolution mechanisms, using their moral authority to discourage extrajudicial violence and promote lawful conduct. Furthermore, addressing the socioeconomic roots of jungle justice such as poverty, unemployment, and illiteracy requires a strong commitment to education, job creation, and targeted poverty alleviation programmes. Legal frameworks should also be reviewed to impose stricter sanctions on perpetrators of mob violence while safeguarding the rights of accused persons to fair hearing and protection under the law.

Ultimately, eradicating jungle justice demands collective responsibility. The police, judiciary, civil society, community leaders, and government must collaborate to restore institutional legitimacy, strengthen the rule of law, and nurture civic values rooted in justice and

empathy. Only through coordinated, inclusive, and sustained action can Ibadan and Nigeria as a whole overcome the culture of mob justice and advance toward a more just, humane, and orderly society.

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